

Analysis of factors associated with the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at the integrated guidance post for non-communicable diseases (Posbindu PTM) in the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

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Abstract

Hypertension is a chronic condition characterized by a persistent elevation in blood pressure. It is classified as a non-communicable disease. Various health services are provided to ensure patient satisfaction. The objective of this study is to analyze the factors associated with the satisfaction of patients with hypertension in Integrated Guidance Post for Non-Communicable Diseases (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. This study employs a quantitative design with a cross-sectional approach and uses accidental sampling as the sampling technique. The study population consists of 98 hypertensive patients who accessed services at the Posbindu PTM. The research instrument used is a questionnaire. The study variables include tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and trust. Data analysis comprises univariate and bivariate analyses using the chi-square test, as well as multivariate analysis using binary logistic regression. The chi-square test results indicate significant associations between patient satisfaction and the variables of tangibles ($p=0.003$), reliability ($p=0.023$), responsiveness ($p=0.03$), assurance ($p=0.016$), empathy ($p=0.001$), and trust ($p=0.03$) in obtaining services at the Posbindu PTM. The binary logistic regression test shows that empathy is the most influential variable, with an Exp(B) value of 8.656. This study demonstrates that the higher the level of empathetic health services provided by the community health center, the greater the satisfaction experienced by hypertensive patients

Keywords: Hypertension; Patient Satisfaction; Health Services; Integrated Guidance Post for Non-Communicable Diseases (Posbindu PTM); Empathy

1. Introduction

According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1.4 billion adults aged 30–79 years worldwide were living with hypertension in 2024, representing about 33% of the global population within that age group. Nearly two-thirds of these individuals reside in low- and middle-income countries, highlighting disparities in access to healthcare services. Among all individuals with hypertension, an estimated 600 million (44%) remain unaware of their condition, while around 630 million (44%) have been diagnosed and are receiving treatment. [1]

Hypertension, or high blood pressure, is a chronic condition characterized by a sustained elevation of blood pressure against the arterial walls, occurring when systolic pressure exceeds 140 mmHg and/or diastolic pressure reaches 90 mmHg or higher. Hypertension is classified as one of the major non-communicable diseases (NCDs). [2]. Hypertension can disrupt the delivery of oxygen and nutrients to bodily tissues, thereby posing a risk of damage to vital organs and potentially leading to fatal outcomes. Elevated blood pressure causes the arterial walls to thicken and stiffen, reducing

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blood flow and oxygen supply to the heart. This condition may trigger serious complications, including heart failure, angina, and even myocardial infarction. [3]

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) have become one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide and represent a major challenge for health systems in the 21st century. In addition, community health centers play an essential role in empowering communities in the health sector to improve overall public health status. One strategic approach in addressing NCDs is through community-based interventions. One of the efforts to control the incidence of NCDs is the direct involvement of the community through the activities of the Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) [4]

Because hypertension can be controlled through various lifestyle-related efforts, one of the key solutions to reduce its incidence is the provision of health education to the community. Delivering accurate information and health education is expected to enhance public knowledge, awareness, and motivation to engage in preventive measures and self-care at home, thereby reducing the incidence of hypertension, particularly among high-risk populations.[5] With the establishment of Posbindu PTM, the community is expected to have easier access to health monitoring services and early disease detection without the need to immediately visit a primary health center. This is particularly important for individuals with hypertension, who ideally should monitor their blood pressure at least once a month. The recommended blood pressure control target is <140/90 mmHg. [6]

Therefore, the availability of healthcare services is crucial for achieving a healthy society. Various health services are provided to facilitate community access to medical care. To become a preferred healthcare provider and gain community loyalty, it is essential for every health service institution to continuously improve the quality of care, thereby enhancing patient satisfaction and achieving an optimal average level of satisfaction. [7] Over time, one of the challenges frequently encountered by Posbindu PTM is the inability to fully meet patients' expectations. Issues such as delayed service delivery and prolonged waiting times often result in services that fall short of what patients anticipate. These conditions can ultimately affect the overall quality of care. [8]

In Kendari City, numerous Posbindu PTM services are available, including those under the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center. Within its working area, there are nine Posbindu PTM units distributed across four sub-districts. Data on hypertensive patient services over the past two years indicate that in 2023, out of 6.951 registered hypertensive patients, the number receiving healthcare services decreased to 3.351 patients (48.21%). In 2024, the total number of hypertensive patients increased to 7.252, with 4.515 patients (62.3%) receiving healthcare services. For 2025, the service target for hypertensive patients is 7.466, and from January to July, 4.024 hypertensive patients have been recorded. (Data from Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center)

Based on the preliminary survey conducted, it was found that some Posbindu units still lack adequate facilities, such as operating in residential yards or house porches that occasionally change locations, having insufficient waiting areas for patients and their families, and experiencing shortages of essential medical equipment, including the unavailability of cholesterol and uric acid test strips on a monthly basis. In addition, many community members still perceive Posbindu PTM as a service intended only for individuals who are ill or who feel unwell. In fact, Posbindu also serves as an early detection facility for identifying potential disease risks, such as hypertension, thereby helping to prevent an annual increase in patient numbers. Consequently, many community members do not fully utilize the available services.

Based on this background, the present study aims to analyze the factors associated with the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in accessing services at the Posbindu PTM within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025.

2. Material and Methods

This study employed a quantitative research design using a cross-sectional method. The study population consisted of hypertensive patients who attended the Posbindu PTM within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City. A total sample of 98 respondents was selected using an accidental sampling technique. The research instrument used was a structured questionnaire. Primary data were collected by distributing the questionnaire to participating patients. [9]

The independent variables in this study are *tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and trust*. [10] Meanwhile, the dependent variable was patient satisfaction. Data analysis consisted of univariate analysis, bivariate analysis using the chi-square test, and multivariate analysis employing binary logistic regression.[11]

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Univariate Analysis

3.1.1. Respondent Characteristics

Table 1 Characteristics of respondents in the study were classified into several categories: age, gender, education, and occupation.

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Presentation (%)
Age	30-39 Years	8	8.1
	40-49 Years	25	25.5
	50-59 Years	65	66.3
Sex	Male	32	32.7
	Female	66	67.3
Education	Elementary School	29	29.6
	Junior High School	17	17.3
	Senior High School / Vocational School	42	42.9
	Diploma	1	1.0
	Bachelor's Degree	7	7.1
	Not School	2	2.0
Occupation.	Government Employees	2	2.0
	Self-employed	2	2.0
	Private Sector Job	21	21.4
	Laborer	3	3.1
	Farmer	12	12.2
	Retired Government Employees	3	3.1
	Housewife	55	56.1

Source: Primary Data 2025

The findings show that among 98 respondents (100%), the highest proportion was in the 50–59-year age group, totaling 65 respondents (66.3%), while the lowest was in the 30–39-year age group with 3 respondents (8.1%). The majority of respondents were female, with 66 individuals (67.3%), and the fewest were male, totaling 32 individuals (32.7%). In terms of education, the highest number of respondents had completed senior high school, amounting to 42 individuals (42.9%), whereas the lowest was at the diploma level with 1 respondent (1%). Regarding occupation, the largest group consisted of housewives, totaling 55 respondents (56.1%), while the smallest groups Government Employees and entrepreneurs, each with 2 respondents (2.0%).

3.1.2. Research Variables

Hypertension Patient Satisfaction

Table 2 shows that, based on the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at the Posbindu PTM in the working area of the UPTD Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025, out of 98 respondents (100%), a total of 78 respondents (79.6%) reported being satisfied, while 20 respondents (20.4%) reported being dissatisfied.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents Based on the Satisfaction of Hypertensive Patients in Receiving Services at the Posbindu PTM in the Working Area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

No.	Hypertension Patient Satisfaction	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Satisfied	78	79.6
2	Not Satisfied	20	20.4
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Tangible

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents Based on Tangibles in Relation to the Satisfaction of Hypertensive Patients in Receiving Services at the Posbindu PTM in the Working Area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025.

No.	Tangible	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	79	80.6
2	Less Good	19	19.4
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 3 shows that, based on the tangibles dimension related to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at the Posbindu PTM in the working area of the UPTD Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025, out of 98 respondents (100%), a total of 79 respondents (80.6%) rated the tangibles as good, while 19 respondents (19.4%) rated them as inadequate.

Reliability

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents Based on Reliability in Relation to the Satisfaction of Hypertensive Patients in Receiving Services at the Posbindu PTM in the Working Area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

No.	Reliability	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	85	86.7
2	Less Good	13	13.3
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 4 illustrates the distribution of respondents based on reliability in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. Of the 98 respondents (100%), 85 respondents (86.7%) reported good reliability, while 13 respondents (13.3%) reported poor reliability

Responsiveness

Table 5 shows the distribution of respondents based on responsiveness in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in accessing services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. Of the 98 respondents (100%), 91 respondents (92.9%) reported good responsiveness, while 7 respondents (7.1%) reported poor responsiveness.

Table 5 The distribution of respondents based on reliability regarding the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025

No.	<i>Responsiveness</i>	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	91	92.9
2	Less Good	7	7.1
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Assurance

Table 6 The distribution of respondents based on assurance regarding the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025

No.	<i>Assurance</i>	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	89	90.8
2	Less Good	9	9.2
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 6 presents the distribution of respondents based on assurance in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. Of the 98 respondents (100%), 89 respondents (90.8%) reported good assurance, while 9 respondents (9.2%) reported poor assurance.

Emphaty

Table 7 Tistribution of respondents based on empathy in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025

No.	<i>Emphaty</i>	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	90	91.8
2	Less Good	8	8.2
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

Table 7 presents the distribution of respondents based on empathy in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in accessing services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. Of the 98 respondents (100%), 90 respondents (91.8%) reported good empathy, while 8 respondents (8.2%) reported poor empathy.

Trust

Table 8 presents the distribution of respondents based on trust in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in accessing services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of UPTD Puskesmas Lepo-Lepo, Kendari City, in 2025. Of the 98 respondents (100%), 84 respondents (85.7%) reported good trust, while 14 respondents (14.3%) reported poor trust.

Table 8 The distribution of respondents based on trust in relation to the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in obtaining services at the Non-Communicable Disease Integrated Guidance Post (Posbindu PTM) within the working area of Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025

No.	Trust	Frequency	Presentation (%)
1	Good	84	85.7
2	Less Good	14	14.3
	Total	98	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2025

3.1.3. Bivariate Analysis

Bivariate analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable using crosstabulations. The statistical test employed in this analysis was the Chi-square test with a 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.05$). A statistically significant association is indicated when the p-value is less than 0.05. [12]

Tangible

Table 9 Association Between Tangible Factors and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Tangible	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Satisfied		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	68	86.1	11	13.9	79	100	0.003
Less Good	10	52.6	9	47.4	19	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 9 shows that among the 79 respondents (100%) who reported good tangible aspects, 68 respondents (86.1%) were satisfied and 11 respondents (13.9%) were not satisfied. Meanwhile, among the 19 respondents (100%) who reported poor tangible aspects, 10 respondents (52.6%) were satisfied and 9 respondents (47.4%) were not satisfied.

Based on the Chi-square statistical test, the p-value obtained was $0.003 < 0.05$, indicating that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant association between tangible factors and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM in the working area of UPTD Puskesmas Lepo-Lepo, Kendari City, in 2025.

Reliability

Table 10 Association Between Reliability and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area of Lepo-Lepo Public Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Reliability	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Not Satisfied		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	71	83,5	14	16.5	85	100	0.023
Less Good	7	53.8	6	46.2	13	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 10 shows that among the 85 respondents (100%) who reported good reliability, 71 respondents (83.5%) were satisfied and 14 respondents (16.5%) were not satisfied. Meanwhile, among the 13 respondents (100%) who reported poor reliability, 7 respondents (53.8%) were satisfied and 6 respondents (46.2%) were not satisfied.

Based on the Chi-square statistical test, the p-value obtained was $0.023 < 0.05$, indicating that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant association between reliability and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM in the working area of UPTD Puskesmas Lepo-Lepo, Kendari City, in 2025.

Responsiveness

Table 11 Association Between Responsiveness and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Responsiveness	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Not Satisfied				
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Good	75	82.4	16	17.6	91	100	0.03
Less Good	3	42.9	4	57.1	7	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 11 shows that among the 91 respondents (100%) who reported good responsiveness, 75 respondents (82.4%) were satisfied and 16 respondents (17.6%) were not satisfied. Meanwhile, among the 7 respondents (100%) who reported poor responsiveness, 3 respondents (42.9%) were satisfied and 4 respondents (57.1%) were not satisfied.

Based on the Chi-square statistical test, the p-value obtained was $0.03 < 0.05$, indicating that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant association between responsiveness and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM in the working area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025.

Assurance

Table 12 Association Between Assurance and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Assurance	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Tidak Puas				
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Good	74	83.1	15	16.9	89	100	0.016
Less Good	4	44.4	5	55.6	9	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 12 shows that among the 89 respondents (100%) who reported good assurance, 74 respondents (83.1%) were satisfied and 15 respondents (16.9%) were not satisfied. Meanwhile, among the 9 respondents (100%) who reported poor assurance, 4 respondents (55.6%) were satisfied and 5 respondents (44.4%) were not satisfied. Based on the Chi-square statistical test, the p-value obtained was $0.016 < 0.05$, indicating that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant association between assurance and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM in the working area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025.

Empathy

Table 13 Association Between Empathy and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Empathy	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Satisfied		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	76	84.4	14	15.6	90	100	0.001
Less Good	2	25	6	75	8	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 13 shows that among the 90 respondents (100%) who reported good empathy, 76 respondents (84.4%) were satisfied and 14 respondents (15.6%) were not satisfied. Meanwhile, among the 8 respondents (100%) who reported poor empathy, 2 respondents (25%) were satisfied and 6 respondents (75%) were not satisfied.

Based on the Chi-square statistical test, the p-value obtained was $0.003 < 0.05$, indicating that the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant association between empathy and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM in the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025.

Trust

Table 13 Association Between Trust and Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM, Working Area the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, 2025

Trust	Satisfied				Amount		p Value
	Satisfied		Satisfied		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Good	70	83.3	14	16.7	84	100	0.035
Less Good	8	57.1	6	42.9	14	100	
Total	78	79.6	20	20.4	98	100	

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

Table 13 indicates that among 84 respondents (100%) who reported high levels of trust, 70 respondents (83.3%) expressed satisfaction, while 14 respondents (16.7%) expressed dissatisfaction. In contrast, among 16 respondents (100%) who reported low levels of trust, 8 respondents (57.1%) expressed satisfaction, and 6 respondents (42.9%) expressed dissatisfaction. Based on the Chi-Square test, the p-value was 0.035, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between trust and the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at Posbindu PTM within the operational area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025.

3.1.4. Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis is employed to examine the simultaneous effects of multiple independent and dependent variables. This analysis aims to identify the variable that has the most dominant influence on the outcome variable. The method applied in this study is binary logistic regression. [13]

Based on the results of the bivariate analysis, the independent variables with p-values < 0.05 were identified as tangible evidence, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and trust. Consequently, these variables were included in the multivariate binary logistic regression analysis..

Table 14 Multivariate Analysis of Factors Influencing Hypertensive Patients' Satisfaction in Receiving Services at Posbindu PTM within the Operational Area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025

Variabel	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
<i>Tangible</i>	.846	.745	1.289	1	.256	2.329
<i>Reliability</i>	.682	.764	.796	1	.372	1.977
<i>Responsiveness</i>	1.225	1.068	1.316	1	.251	3.405
<i>Assurance</i>	1.385	.908	2.324	1	.127	3.994
<i>Empathy</i>	2.158	.994	4.714	1	.030	8.656
<i>Trust</i>	.466	.761	.375	1	.540	1.593

Source: Results of Data Analysis using SPSS Application, 2025

The results indicate that the most influential factor on hypertensive patients' satisfaction in receiving services at Posbindu PTM within the operational area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025 is the empathy variable, with a significance value of $0.014 < 0.05$ and an Exp(B) value of 8.656. This demonstrates that patients who perceive higher levels of empathy have an 8.6 times greater likelihood of satisfaction compared to other variables. From the multivariate statistical analysis, it can be concluded that the higher the level of empathy provided by the health center to patients, the greater the satisfaction experienced by the patients..

Hypertensive patients often experience anxiety related to the risk of complications such as stroke or heart failure. When healthcare personnel demonstrate empathy, provide reassuring explanations, and show a willingness to assist, a sense of security is established, directly impacting patient satisfaction. Hypertensive individuals heavily rely on adherence to medication, diet, and lifestyle modifications. Personnel who are able to empathize tend to be more effective in delivering easily understandable education and in motivating patients. This ease of communication strengthens trust and supports satisfaction with the services provided at Posbindu PTM

These findings are also consistent with the study by Afigah & Ispandiyah (2025), which identified the empathy dimension as having the most significant influence (Sig. 0.004) on patient satisfaction at Puskesmas Mantrijeron, Yogyakarta City, in 2024. This indicates that patients at Puskesmas Mantrijeron prioritize consistent services that receive personal attention from healthcare providers over other factors. In the context of primary healthcare services, such as those provided by community health centers, personal interaction is particularly important, as patients expect treatment that is humane and attentive. [14]

These findings are also consistent with the study conducted by Haeruddin (2021). The multivariate analysis of independent variables examined simultaneously indicated that the most influential factor on the likelihood of inpatient patients returning to RSUD Haji Makassar, after being affected by satisfaction, was empathy, with a significance value of ($\rho = 0.000$) and an Exp(B) value of 77.000 [15]

4. Conclusion

The findings of the study indicate a significant association between tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and trust with the satisfaction of hypertensive patients in receiving services at the Posbindu PTM in the working area of the Lepo-Lepo Community Health Center, Kendari City, in 2025. Each variable demonstrated a p-value below 0.05, specifically $p=0.003$ for *tangibles*, $p=0.023$ for *reliability*, $p=0.03$ for *responsiveness*, $p=0.016$ for *assurance*, $p=0.001$ for *empathy*, and $p=0.03$ for *trust*. Among these variables, *empathy* emerged as the most influential factor affecting patient satisfaction, as evidenced by the *binary logistic regression* analysis showing an Odds Ratio Exp(B) of 8.656. This indicates that patients who perceived a higher level of empathy had approximately 8.6 times greater likelihood of being satisfied with the services received.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interest were identified in this study

Statement of informed consent

As a researcher, I affirm that I have provided complete, clear, and comprehensible information to the prospective participant regarding the objectives of the study, the procedures to be undertaken, the potential benefits and risks, the principles of data confidentiality, as well as the participant's right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. I ensure that the entire process of obtaining informed consent is conducted ethically, voluntarily, without coercion, and in accordance with established research ethics standards. Accordingly, I guarantee that the participant has received sufficient information to make an informed and responsible decision regarding their participation in this study

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